

1. DATA SUMMARY

DOI	Name of the dataset	Work Package (Task)
10.5281/zenodo.113514	D1.3 Sustainability assessment model	WP1
Principal type of data contained in the data set		
<input type="checkbox"/> Quantitative <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Numeric <input type="checkbox"/> Text <input type="checkbox"/> Images <input type="checkbox"/> Audio <input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Databases <input type="checkbox"/> Non-structured data <input type="checkbox"/> Source code <input type="checkbox"/> Computational models <input type="checkbox"/> Time series <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Vector data	
Data description		
<p>Please, describe the data to be collected. Please specify the type and provide a short description of every field contained in the data. Moreover, add information about the size of the data set, format, etc.</p> <p>Information retrieved to build the Baseline. Its contains: * Spatial database formed by a set vector data in shapefile format. * Tabular Information about the state of the waste management system in all the pilot sites</p>		
What is the source of the data?		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Field work <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Direct measurements <input type="checkbox"/> Surveys <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Simulations	<input type="checkbox"/> Expert Knowledge, <input type="checkbox"/> Model Output <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Data Estimation, Oficial Databases	
Methodology used to collect this data		
<p>Please briefly describe the processes or methods which have been used to get the data.</p> <p>Waste generation: filling sensors, data estimation, field work Route: GPS, digitalization, simulation Deposit point: GPS, field work</p>		
Relation to the data with the objectives of the project		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reduce the generation of RSU. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Increase the management of waste in favour of reusing and recycling. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reduce the waste to landfill. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reduce the management cost. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reduce the generation of GHG emissions. <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Baseline data for the KPIs calculation		
Relation to the data with the results of the project		
<u>Operation and Planning:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Operation and Management Module. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collection Module. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Planning Module. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Circular Economy Module. <u>APPs:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Food App. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local Trade App. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizen App. <u>Educational Materials:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Innovative Teaching Units. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sorting Game. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Eco-design Game. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Planning Game. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Virtual City Game.	<u>Citizen Science:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Eco-design solutions. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Planning solutions. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Circular economy solutions. <u>Prevention and Best Practices:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic instruments: New Pay-As-you-Throw (PAYT) schemes and incentives. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Innovative awareness actions including web-based tools for dissemination. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Best Practice Book. <u>New Treatments:</u> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pre-dried and shredded bio-waste. Bio-fuel and compost production plant.#	
Why is this data collected?		
<p>Please, contextualize the information collected.</p> <p>This information is needed to built the baseline of waste management systems per pilot.</p>		
Please, provide a brief description of any external dataset used		
<p>For every external data set used please explain its origin, relevance and license.</p> <p>Official databases</p>		

2. FAIR DATA (DATA FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSE)

2.1. DATA FINDABLE

Tim's 5-star classification of the dataset	
<input type="checkbox"/> Data is available under an open license <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use a structured data (e.g., Excel instead of image scan of a table) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Is available in a non-proprietary open format (e.g., CSV as well as of Excel) <input type="checkbox"/> Use URIs to denote things <input type="checkbox"/> The data is linked to other data to provide context	
Metadata standards	
<p>Please cite the standard and format use for the date. If any this data set does not follow any standardized format, please provide a formal specification. For example, the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, Inspire Initiative, ISO, etc.</p> <p>Inspire Initiative</p> <p>Link regarding to metadata standard: http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/</p>	
Documentation stored in the data	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Information of the origin of the data <input type="checkbox"/> Codebook <input type="checkbox"/> List of abbreviations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Description of variables <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technical information about files <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Ontologies	
<input type="checkbox"/> FIWARE Link regarding to fiware https://www.fiware.org/data-models	<input type="checkbox"/> Other external ontology Link regarding to ontologies https://www.w3.org/wiki/Lists_of_ontologies <input type="checkbox"/> Our defined ontology (please specify):
Whom might it be useful?	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public Administrations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research groups <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citizens	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Private sector <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Channels to reach potential users	
<input type="checkbox"/> Personal/research group web page <input type="checkbox"/> Well-known specialist database <input type="checkbox"/> Search Administration database <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Email of corresponding author	<input type="checkbox"/> Data access statement in published articles <input type="checkbox"/> Personal networking <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citation of data sets <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Waste4Think website Zenodo

2.2. DATA ACCESSIBLE

Accessibility	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public data	<input type="checkbox"/> Confidential data
Obligation or intention to publish/share data	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
When will the data be published?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Immediately on collection <input type="checkbox"/> Within sometime after the ends of the project (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> Within sometime after its collection (please specify):	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To coincide with publication of main results <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): Publication of Deliverable D1.3
Expected difficulties file sharing	
<input type="checkbox"/> Confidentiality <input type="checkbox"/> Large file size <input type="checkbox"/> Ownership/licensing	<input type="checkbox"/> Intended commercialisation <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify): None

2.3. DATA INTEROPERABLE

File format			
Spreadsheet: <input type="checkbox"/> ODS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> XLS <input type="checkbox"/> CSV Documentation <input type="checkbox"/> DOC <input type="checkbox"/> PDF <input type="checkbox"/> TXT <input type="checkbox"/> HTML	Structured data <input type="checkbox"/> XML <input type="checkbox"/> JSON Geographical data <input type="checkbox"/> DXF <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SHP <input type="checkbox"/> GEOJSON	Image: <input type="checkbox"/> JPG <input type="checkbox"/> TIFF <input type="checkbox"/> PNG Video: <input type="checkbox"/> WEBM <input type="checkbox"/> MP4 <input type="checkbox"/> MKZ	Other (please specify):
Methods or software tools needed to access the data			
Please detail any necessary software to manipulate the information (if not standard). Geographic information system (GIS) SpreadSheet software able to open xls files			

2.4. DATA REUSE

License conditions and restrictions	
<input type="checkbox"/> Copyright <input type="checkbox"/> Creative Commons (please specify)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open Licence (please specify): <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Please, list the owners of the copyright and intellectual property involved	
The authors of the document. Public Authorities. OpenStreetMap contributors	
Access permissions and restrictions	
List roles/individuals (internal & external) with any limitations to access (e.g. scope, actions permitted), including who has authority to grant additional access. None.	

3. DATA MANAGEMENT AND ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Partners	Collection	Curation	Preservation
Foundation Deusto.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Zabala Innovation Consulting S.A.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Town hall of Zamudio	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Association of industries cluster environment Euskadi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green Technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enbio Epe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
National Technical University of Athens-NTUA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University of Patras	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dimos Chalandriou	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Serious Games Interactive APS	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ars Ambiente SRL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Comune di Seveso	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Legambiente Lombardia Onlus	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Softline SRL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Moba Mobile Automation AG	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EMAC Municipal enterprise environment Cascais	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Urban Ecology Agency of Barcelona	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?			
None			

How will these be covered?	
Primary storage medium and location	
<input type="checkbox"/> University shared or research storage <input type="checkbox"/> Secure facility from a data provider <input type="checkbox"/> Physical storage <input type="checkbox"/> Cloud platforms (e.g. Github) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Last resort platforms (e.g. Zenodo)	<input type="checkbox"/> Academic research network platforms (e.g. ResearchGate). <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional open data repositories (e.g. CKAN based) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):
Link regarding to data repositories: http://www.re3data.org/	
Data curation processes	
Please briefly describe the management of data throughout its life cycle. The data will be updated, modified and corrected during the monitoring carried out in the project	
How will long-term preservation and access be assured?	
Please briefly describe how the data will be preserved after the end of the project. Stored in ZENODO	
Regularity of backups and data performed. Replicas in other different places (if any)	
For D1.3, no backup of data is needed, as it's not a dynamic database.	
File management versioning	
<input type="checkbox"/> Unnecessary (i.e. overwrite original file) <input type="checkbox"/> Control version software (e.g. Git, please specify):	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Date/version number in filename/folder <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify):

4. ETHICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS

Ethical aspect (If know)
<input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (briefly describe): Aspects regarding informed consent in data collection and information protection in data storage and access. (Fulfillment of Ethical requirements are detailed in D9.1 – D9.7). The census data to perform the accessibility and proximity analysis have been anonymised
Legal aspect (If know)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (briefly describe):

5. OTHER ASPECTS

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